

Biomimetic Cilia-based MEMS Sensors for Underwater Applications - A Review

B. Abdul^{*1}, S. Abdul², A. R. Asary³

¹Sabancı University, 34956 Tuzla, İstanbul, Turkey

²NED university of Engineering and technology, 79270, Karachi, Pakistan

³University of Naples Parthenope Italy, 80133 Napoli, Italy

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*Corresponding Author:

B. Abdul

abdul.basit@sabanciuniv.edu

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Natural organisms such as fish, arthropods and ear have excellent sensory receptors like later line system, filiform hairs and basilar membrane respectively. Researchers have developed various type of mechanical sensors, inspired by nature creatures. A review on biomimetic cilia and Micro-Electro-Mechanical-Systems (MEMS) developments for underwater sensing robotics is presented. In this paper, MEMS technologies for building artificial hair cell sensors using representative material systems, briefly outlines of their fabrication method and performance have been explained. We categorize the developed artificial cilia-based sensors into different types according to their transduction mechanism to they based on, for example, piezo resistive and piezoelectric effects.

Keywords: BIOMIMETIC CILIA, SENSORY RECEPTORS, LATERAL LINE SYSTEM , MEMS, ARTIFICIAL HAIR

1. Introduction

Human technological developments have always been inspired by nature. Some of the significant skills of the existing animals can be a rich source of inspiration for humans to develop their counterparts, allowing potential applications in different fields [1, 2]. In the recent decades, increasing attentions from scholars and scientists have been focused on the astonishing features of mechanoreceptors of animals [1]. Mechanoreceptors with different geometric structures are used by animals

to obtain information from surrounding environment and to convert them into biological signals, which play critical role for their survival [3, 4]. For example, lateral line system in the fish and sensory hair on the body surface of spiders, scorpions and crickets helped them to recognize external stimuli and generate corresponding responses [5]. Mimicking these outstanding biological mechanoreceptors therefore offers different techniques and methods for designing advanced artificial hair-sensors as an innovative and

preferential architecture as a hydrophone in water.

Cilia are microtubule-based organelles like antennae in the surface of cells of the body. In most of the biological structures, cilia have length from 7 μm to 50 μm and diameter of about 250 nm [1]. There are two types of cilia: motile cilia, which constantly beat in a single direction, and non-motile cilia, which typically serve as sensory organelles. The cilia play an important role in feeding the mollusks in sessile organisms. It is the cilia that is working in unison in the human body to produce a wave-like movement, which bend the mucus from the lining of lungs [1]. Mechanoreceptors with different geometric structures are used by animals to obtain information from surrounding and convert them into biological signals, which play critical role for their survival [6, 7]. Lateral line system in the fish and sensory hair on the body surface of spider, scorpions and crickets helped them to recognize external stimuli and make corresponding responses [5].

Micro-Electro- Mechanical Systems (MEMS) technology has attracted great attention for researchers in biomimetic cilia-based devices design. Because of high effectiveness in the microfabrication process of MEMS technologies, advantages such as miniaturization, efficient frequency response and high sensitivity in hydrophones are obtained [8]. Piezoelectric thin films are one of the most prominent technologies in developing nanoscale and microscale devices due to the added functionality provided by the electromechanical coupling and the ability of piezoelectric materials to be micro-machined [9]. Among piezoelectric polycrystalline films, AlN is a promising active material due to its properties. AlN exhibits piezoelectric coefficients lower than that of PZT thin films but comparable with ZnO films; however, it has low dielectric constant and high Young's modulus, which result in improved electromechanical coupling coefficient against PZT [10].

Piezoelectric hydrophone are the most common underwater acoustic devices used to detect the pressure variations of acoustic signals and noise in the water and to produce an output voltage proportional to the pressure. Therefore, it plays an increasingly vital role in sonar systems, submarine resources exploration and underwater noise monitoring [11, 12]. The first micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) vector hydrophone was reported in 1996 as a directional acoustic sensor [13]. Since then, MEMS hydrophone, in which thin film of piezoelectric material is used as sensing elements, has been exploited in different types of underwater robotics [14, 15]. Recently, a directional hydrophone at ultrasonic frequencies with four resonant upwards bent cantilevers in a cross-configuration exploiting AlN as piezoelectric material embedded between Molybdenum (Mo) electrodes have been reported [16] and a novel algorithm was introduced [17]. This hydrophone design was inspired by fish lateral line cilia-based mechanoreceptors [18].

Here, this review is to provide the readers with a broad overview by outlining the developments of biomimetic sensors in the last few years, with special emphasis on artificial cilia based sensors that were inspired by the sensory hair receptors in lateral line system of fishes, basilar membrane in ear and arthropods. Besides, the basic morphology, sensing mechanism, mechanical model of biological receptors are shed lights on too, in order to provide a comprehensive understanding for readers who are interested in.

2. Biomimetic natural-cilia in fish (lateral line organ)

2.1 Bionic principle

The lateral line of the fish is a peculiar sensory organ, which consists of cilia-based mechanoreceptors called neuromasts. A jelly like cupola covered these cilia, which are situated in the canals along the body or on the skin of the fish (Figure 1a, 1b, 1c). Acoustic waves through fluid motion gets through pores into the lateral line canal, filled with mucus, and deliver the mechanical force to each single mechanoreceptor. The deformation in the hair cell occurs because of the fluid motion of the mucus. Figure 1d illustrates sense-conducting pathway of a fish's lateral line organ. Consequently, the sensory cells are stimulated and transmit the signal to medulla oblongata by nerve fiber, which is the sensory pathway of fish lateral line organs [19].

Figure 1. (a) Structure of fish lateral line. (b) Configuration of canal. (c) A close up of a neuromast Reprinted with permission from [19] (d) Sensing mechanism pathway of a fish's lateral line organ.

2.2 artificial-cilia based piezoresistive mems sensors for underwater application

A review on design and optimization of stress centralized MEMS vector hydrophone was reported [20] in which three different microstructure were described: centralized vector hydrophone, conventional four-beam vector hydrophone and lollipop-shaped hydrophone were analyzed. Principle of operation of these hydrophones were based on piezoresistive effect inspired by the lateral line of a fish and its structures. Different types of piezoresistive vector hydrophone have been developed so far as shown in table 1. Most papers have used Finite Element Methods (FEM) for modeling and simulation of hydrophone based on a hair design. It was concluded that placing a piezo-resistor in the maximum stressed region of a hair-like structure, it can experience the maximum change in resistivity and thus maximum change in voltage output, improving the sensitivity to flow. The resonant frequency of the hydrophone is dependent upon its design. The resonance frequency of a MEMS device in liquid is different from that in air due to the fluid-structure interaction (FSI). Based on the theory of Fluid-Solid Coupling, fluid can be described as a generalized distributed mass attached on the micro-structure, which results in the resonance frequency of the microstructure in the liquid being lower than that in the air.

The fabrication techniques of a hair-based vector hydrophone consist of manufacturing a rigid plastic North American Academic Research, 4(12) | December 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5768208> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 13

cylinder, using plastic molding processing, on a four-beam microstructure using a SOI wafer by MEMS technology. The four-beam configuration provides directional response in order to find out the acoustics source direction in water. This structure is placed inside a polymeric capsule, mimicking the cupula structure. It can be concluded that the only suitable material for encapsulating the four-beam structure is polyurethane and the working medium for submerging the cylinder inside the encapsulation is silicone oil or castor oil. The development of a differential MEMS vector hydrophone was reported [21] in which double cilium was introduced as piezo-resistive artificial hair cell for underwater acoustics. Even if the architecture is quite similar to the previous artificial hair cells designs, in this hydrophone the working principle is obtained by two parallel cantilevers connected together with a perpendicular structure. The two cantilevers bend together and in their hinges, two piezo-resistances are placed. The structure will be orthogonally placed with respect the sound impinging direction, as an acoustic antenna. Theoretically, the amplitude of the output signals of the sensitive microstructure is not determined by the acceleration signals, but completely by the acoustic signals, which has a high sensitivity up to -185 dB with ability to find underwater acoustic detection. Table 1 shows summary of different cantilever based piezoresistive MEMS hydrophone with their dimensions, sensitivity, and frequency bandwidth.

Reference	Transduction Mechanism	Cantilevers (L x W x T) μm	Sensitivity (dB)	Frequency Band Width	Major Sensing Materials
[20]	Piezo-resistive	1000 x 120 x 30	-200	@ 500 Hz	Au, SiN, Si
[29]	Piezo-resistive	1000 x 120 x 10	-197.7	5Hz-2kHz	TiPtAuSiO ₂
[30]	Piezo-resistive	5000 x 200	-197.2	40Hz-400Hz	SIOAu Bo
[31]	Piezo-resistive	1000 x 120 x 10	-197	NA	Si, SiO ₂ , Bo
[19]	Piezo-resistive	1500 x 130 x 20	-192	@ 1kHz	SOI, Ti, Pt, Bo
[21]	Piezo-resistive	1000 x 120 x 40	-185	@ 500 Hz	SOI, Au
[32]	Piezo-resistive	NA	-184.6	@1 kHz	GaAs, AlAs
[33]	Piezo-resistive	1500 x 200 x 100	-180	25Hz-1.5Hz	Au, Bo, Pt
[34]	Piezo-resistive	1500 x 130 x 20	-180	20Hz-2kHz	SOI, Au, Bo
[19]	Piezo-resistive	3500 x 130 x 20	-180	20Hz-2.5kHz	SOI, Ti, Pt, Au,
[35]	Piezo-resistive	NA	-178	20Hz-2kHz	SIOAu Bo
[11]	Piezo-resistive	1000 x 120 x 15	-170	40Hz-4kHz	Ga, Caster oil
[36]	Piezo-resistive	5000 x 150	-165	20Hz-2kHz	Fiber, Plastic

Table 1. Summary of piezo resistive MEMS Hydrophone for underwater for sensing

2.3 artificial-cilia based piezoelectric mems sensor for underwater application

Besides piezo resistive materials, piezoelectricity effect has been exploited for vector hydrophone design. In order to enhanced the sensitivity of the hydrophone to sound direction, different diaphragms structures like square, rectangular and circular were shown to achieve directional optimization: a study on three different piezoelectric materials PZT, PVDF and ZnO was carried out [22]. A theoretical model of a piezoelectric vector hydrophone was proposed in [23] as previously inspired by the hair cell structure in nature. In this work, the sensing principle is based on four different diaphragms made by PZT (lead zirconate titanate) as piezoelectric material placed underneath a bending pillar. This hydrophone had sensitivity of -191dB, which is able to find the direction of underwater sound at low frequencies. Recently, a four-beam vector

hydrophone [24] exploited piezoelectric PZT as functional layer. Exploiting simulation results, the piezoelectric films are optimally distributed at the tip of the four beams where the maximum strain locates. The microstructure was fabricated by standard MEMS process on the wafer substrate. The major process include oxidation, sputtering, sol-gel, photoetching, ICP reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE), and chemical vapor deposition. This hydrophone can work in the frequency range of 20–2000 Hz with sensitivity up to –189.3 dB and shows good directivity pattern, allowing finding underwater acoustic source direction.

2.3.1 Stress-driven cantilever-based hydrophone

The structure of biomimetic vector hydrophone is based on a design that connects two mechanical components together in a so-called "stress-driven" upwards bent cantilever, rather than combining a flat beam and a rigid vertical pillar. The technological principle of such “stress-driven” artificial hair like sensor mainly relies on a stress gradient from deposition conditions, leading to tensile or compressive intrinsic stress [18] allowing different “out-of-plane” bending in upward or downwards direction. Thus, vector hydrophone based on stress-driven structure, developed with piezoelectric or piezoresistive materials, will work as an artificial hair like sensor, sensitive to underwater acoustics in the desired range of the device [25, 26, 27].

A novel high sensitive piezoelectric cantilever-based micro electro mechanical system (MEMS) ultrasonic vector hydrophone has realized by a biomimetic approach. The hydrophone consists of four cantilevers in a cross shape configuration made by aluminum nitride (AlN) as piezoelectric thin film of 1 μm and 2 μm were embedded between top and bottom Molybdenum (Mo) electrodes of 200 nm [16, 17]. Four different readout mechanism of directionality are described [16] with a novel algorithm which help to detect the underwater acoustic source direction in a ultrasonic frequency range from 20 kHz to 200 kHz. This is a first ultrasonic directional hydrophone based on AlN piezoelectric four cantilevers in a cross-shape configuration.

The simulation modeling has been performed using COMSOL Multiphysics FEM software, implementing the piezoelectric constitutive equations. Piezoelectricity is the ability of the materials to generate electric charges in response to an applied mechanical stress (direct effect) or, vice versa, to undergo a deformation in response to an applied electrical field (inverse effect). When the applied force on the material is removed, the polarization disappears and the material comes back to its original equilibrium. The piezoelectricity is mathematically described by the coupling of electric and elastic phenomena. Therefore, the constitutive relations can be written as relationship between mechanical quantities (stress T_{ij} or strain S_{ij}) and electrical quantities (electric field E_k or polarization P_k). A first relationship can be formulated referring to the electrical polarization generated by the material, both for stress and strain, as follows [16, 17, 28].

$$P_k = dk_{ij} T_{ij} \quad (1) \quad \text{Polarization in Stress-Charge Form}$$

$$P_k = ek_{ij} S_{ij} \quad (2) \quad \text{Polarization in Strain-Charge Form}$$

where [d] and [e] are the tensors of the coupling piezoelectric coefficients for stress (in SI, C/N) and strain (in SI, C/m²), respectively. At the same time, an electric field applied to the material causes a stress and a strain that are expressed as follows:

$$T_{ij} = e_{ijk} E_k \quad (3)$$

$$S_{ij} = d_{ijk} E_k \quad (4)$$

where the indices i, j and k represent the three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system.

In this design, simulations of cantilever microstructures with different length are performed in the range from 100 μm to 1000 μm , keeping the width constant at 70 μm , to study the effect of length on first resonance frequency mode in both water and air. Solid mechanics, electrostatic and pressure acoustic are the physics used to study the behavior of the micro cantilevers. The multilayered structure of the micro cantilevers consist of different

materials: a thin piezoelectric layer of AlN (1 μm) was embedded between top and bottom electrodes of aluminum (Mo) (200 nm each). Finally, a parylene coating of 1 μm thickness was added on both sides to prevent short circuits in water. Finite element analysis (FEA) design allows to set up the cantilever first resonant mode in the desired underwater ultrasonic frequency range from 2 kHz to 200 kHz. Table 2 shows the mechanical properties of the materials and their thickness, used to design and simulate the micro cantilevers.

Reference	Transduction Mechanism	Cantilevers (L x W x T) μm	Sensitivity (dB)	Detection Range	Frequency Band Width	Major Sensing Materials
[37]	Commercial	Needle-based	-211	NA	20Hz-180kHz	NA
[22]	Piezo-electric	3000 x 320 x 320	-191	NA	@ 10.4 kHz	PZT
[24]	Piezo-electric	1000 x 150 x 30	-189	NA	20Hz-2kHz	PZT
[16]	Piezo-electric	300 x 70 x 2.4	-163	NA	20kHz-200kHz	Mo, AlN
[17]	Piezo-electric	300 x 70 x 2.4	-153	NA	20kHz-200kHz	Mo, AlN
[38]	Piezo-electric	200	NA	NA	@ 41.6 kHz	AlN
[39]	Piezo-electric	2700 x 400	NA	0.015ms ⁻¹	NA	SU-8,Si,Au
[8]	Piezo-electric	2000 x 2000 x 7	NA	8.2 mms ⁻¹	@35Hz	PDMS, Cr,
[40]	Piezo-electric	2000 x 2000 x 7	NA	3 mms ⁻¹	0.1Hz-100Hz	Au PDMS,SiO ₂

Table 2. Summary of MEMS piezo electric Hydrophone for underwater for sensing

3. Biomimetic natural-cilia in ear (basilar membrane)

The cochlea is a sensory hair and key organ of basilar membrane. Figure 2a shows a schematic diagram of the human auditory system. Incoming acoustic pressure to tympanic membrane is transmitted to the cochlea through the ossicles. The pressure creates a traveling wave inside the fluid filled cochlea that is separated by the BM. The BMs have different sizes in term of width, thickness, and stiffness along the longitudinal direction. The apical region responds to low-frequency sound [41, 42, 43] while the basal region responds to high-frequency sound. The organ of Corti, which is located on the BM is shown in Figure 2b. Deflection of the stereocilia bundle of the outer sensory hair cells are caused by the vibration of BM. The ionic channel is

then opened and the action potential is generated to stimulate the auditory nerve. Finally, the auditory cortex received the bioelectrical signal allowing to detect the acoustic sounds of various frequencies [44].

Figure 2. (a) Schematic diagram of the human auditory system. (b) Schematic representation of the organ of Corti. Reprinted with permission from [44]. (c) A 3D drawing of the piezoelectric xylophone transducer with the flexible parylene gold connection. The inset shows the details of the xylophone transducer Reprinted with permission from [38].

3.1 Artificial-cilia based mems flowsensors

A miniaturized multi-resonant device inspired by basilar membrane was design and fabricated using MEMS techniques [38]. The transducer can work in both air and underwater and is suitable as a micro hydrophone for in vivo testing in liquid environment. The transducer consists of an array of AlN bimorph cantilevers as shown Figure 2c with varied lengths whose resonances are tuned to a desired frequency range using FEA modeling. AlN is used as piezoelectric layer between bottom electrode of Ti/Pt and top electrode of Cr/Au. Both material and sensor characterization are performed for xylophone transducer. Actuation testing confirmed the transducer functionality was in good agreement as predicted by FEA modeling, hence this device can be used as an intracochlear transducer.

Flexible artificial basilar membrane (FABM) composed of ten-channel cantilevers array, made of piezoelectric AlN on an SU substrate are reported [41]. Each cantilever has different length and used to control the mechanical frequency selectively. The shortest and longest cantilevers have resonance frequencies corresponding to those of the basal and apical regions of the Basilar membrane, respectively. These cantilevers are fabricated by standard MEMS techniques having length from 1380 μm to 2800 μm . Acoustic stimuli of FABM were in agreement with the results of electrical stimuli in range of 659.4-2375Hz.

4. Biomimetic natural-cilia in arthropods (cricket and spider)

Spider has sensory hairs, which are in few micrometer and nearly 2 mm in length. Among these sensory hairs, most of them are mechanosensitive and some of them are chemosensitive [45]. These hairs act as mechanical interfaces for spider, which record external force and convert it into neural signal, and sent to the central nervous system. Airflow or physical forces from surrounding medium cause the bending of the hair shaft. The

hair is strained because of the membrane of the dendrites attached to the base. This in turn modifies the membrane's conductivity, which leads to action potentials sent to the central nervous system provided the stimulus was strong enough [46]. Artificial cilia based on MEMS technology inspired by biomimetic hair of spider was reported [46]. This artificial cilium was fabricated on SOI wafer with SU-8 epoxy and piezoresistive strain gauge. The artificial cilium has 80 μm diameter and 800 μm length. The device was made in pairs oriented at 90° to each other which detect 2-axis flow. The test results shows that device is able to detect flow rate sensitivity of 2 mm/s.

Cricket used mechanoreceptive sensory hairs for acoustics sensing, which are called filiform hairs. These sensory hairs are highly sensitive to low frequency sound with low energy. The sensory hairs are located on the back of the cricket's body on appendices called cerci [47]. The hairs vary in length up to around 1 mm, with concentrations about 150 and 750 μm [48]. Every individual hair is wedged in a cavity, which control the hair to move in a preferred direction. The hair is held in its socket by an elastic material surrounding the base. Airflow stimulates the neuron by rotation of the hair base. By using the collective neural information of all the sensory hairs, the cricket is able to detect the sound of low frequency at any given direction [49]. Arrays of MEMS flow sensors inspired by sensory hair of crickets have been designed fabricated and characterized [50]. The hairs are fixed on suspended membranes with normal translational and rotational degrees of freedom, which consist of SU-8 structures up to 1 mm long. These are fabricated by using MEMS technology. Frequency response of artificial cilia was measured in differential mode and maximum output was obtained at 75 Hz. The device shows directional flow-sensitivity in the form of eight-shape

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this review, we briefly overviewed directional MEMS sensors for underwater applications inspired by biomimetic approach of fish lateral line system, basilar membrane in ear and sensory hairs on body surface of the arthropods. This review illustrates the development of biomimetic cilia based two main MEMS sensors including piezoelectric and piezoresistive devices and studied their performance based on design, material selection and sensitivity. A brief insight on stress-driven approach to design, fabricates, and characterizes the MEMS cantilever based hydrophone for underwater application has been discussed in detail. A controllable stress gradient along the cross section of thin film of piezoelectric aluminum nitride layer can be induced by appropriately designing and micromachining multilayered thin films. Because of AlN piezoelectric stress layer ultrasonic hydrophones have higher performance in term of sensitivity and directionality, with a potential high impact on a wide range of technological underwater applications. Acoustic sounds in all the direction can be determined through Omni directionality pattern. Future development on stress-driven bio-inspired technology will be directed towards large area systems for underwater robotics and ultrasonic applications. Bio-inspired basilar membrane devices could be designed as an array of sensors and ultrasonic generators for underwater applications. Undoubtedly, biomimetic cilia research with the development of MEMS technology will generate a large variety of new and exciting achievements.

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